

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Forecasting Existential Risks: Evidence from a Long Run Forecasting Tournament", Applied Stream

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 David Reinstein Anca Hanea

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper “Forecasting Existential Risks: Evidence from a Long Run Forecasting Tournament”^[1]. This paper was evaluated as part of our “applied and policy stream”, described [here](#). To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

23 Sep 2024 note: The above link to the paper is not currently working. As a backup, see [here](#) or the ('Wayback machine') Web Archive [here](#).

Evaluations

1. [Anonymous evaluation 1](#)
2. [Anonymous evaluation 2](#)

Overall ratings

Note: Applied and Policy Stream

This paper was evaluated as part of our “applied and policy stream”, described [here](#). The ratings should not be directly compared to those in our main academic stream.

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria. *Note:* The second evaluator was given an updated form geared specifically for our [Applied and Policy stream](#), while the first evaluator used the (very similar) interface intended for the academic stream.

I. Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):¹ On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note:* 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Anonymous evaluation 1	75	4.0
Anonymous evaluation 2	80	N/A

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).²

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.³

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

I really appreciate the team's ambitions for tackling difficult long-term forecasts of important existential risks. Just as importantly, they are exploring how experts might update their forecasts when confronted with arguments from peers. Of course there are many methodological challenges to credibly eliciting forecasts for events far into the future, and the researchers do their best to meet them, but it might still fall short. The policy implications of the results so far could also be further clarified.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This report considers a forecasting tournament in which experts in relevant domains and super-forecasters from previous tournaments are asked to predict a large number of quantities of interest related to existential threats to human existence on Earth. A third group, taken from the public more widely, is also consulted. The tournament structure involves several rounds with interaction within and between groups in online forums, sharing anonymised predictions and rationales, rewards for active individuals and assessment of the quality of predictions in terms of how well individuals could predict the values given by others and accuracy on quantities to be revealed over short time horizons.

As an exercise it is very interesting and could potentially be valuable, both to society in general and perhaps decision makers at various levels. It is written appropriately for a relatively non-technical audience, with most of the detail contained in the appendices. The methodology used is consistent with best practice in the literature for this type of tournament, although as the report points out there are question areas where they had to make decisions based on inconclusive research such as predictions for low probability events. Overall, I enjoyed reading the document and found that the summaries do for the most part match the data collected. I do think the report would benefit from revision, based on the comments in my full report.

Metrics

Ratings

	Evaluator 1*		Evaluator 2
	Anonymous		Anonymous

Rating category*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)
Overall assessment ⁴	75	(60, 90)	80
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁵	75	(60, 90)	85
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁶	70	(60, 80)	75
Logic & communication ⁷	80	(70, 90)	75
Open, collaborative, replicable ⁸	70	(60, 80)	85
Real-world relevance ⁹ /Relevance to global priorities ¹⁰ **	90	(85, 95)	95

- Evaluator 1 was given a form following the categories described below, and explained in detail [here](#), with guidance. Evaluator 2 was given the updated form [here](#), with slightly different categories and guidelines, aimed at our [Applied stream](#). Evaluator 2 opted to give midpoint ratings only, not CIs.

** The final categories (Real-world.../Relevance) were separate for Evaluator 1 (although they gave the same ratings for both). These were combined for Evaluator 2, as per our new evaluation template.

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.¹¹

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 5.0)

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 	

Evaluation manager's discussion

Anca Hanea's comments and summary

The Research

- What will the next century bring in terms of grave risks humanity faces and how [do] "we"* evaluate and perceive such risks (nuclear weapons, pandemics, AI)?
 - *(“We” =) college graduates, specialists, and superforecasters (people who are known for accurate predictions of future events) were involved in a forecasting tournament in a few experimental conditions
- The tournament followed state of the art guidance on interaction between and within groups, anonymized predictions and rationales, incentives
- Summary measures were considered when aggregating the different groups predictions:, e.g., the median expert/superforecaster predicted a 6%/1% chance of human extinction by 2100
- Correlations between answers across topics, within groups were considered (but not properly measured)
- The benefits of rationales and discussion were considered

The Evaluations

- Both evaluators applauded the initiative and outlined the difficulty of the task at hand.
- Data sharing was suggested
- Criticism of the design and implementation in terms of questions framing, definition of expertise, lack of training, rare events description
- Criticism of the statistical/quant analysis: CI not capturing the uncertainty properly, dependence measures not estimated, statistical inference not performed, aggregation methods not appropriate

Impact

- Interesting and potentially valuable as an exercise and experimental design

- [Hanea perceives the] Most impact in [terms of the insights into] designing and identifying challenges and complications with such predictions
- Impact through the lessons learned in analysing such data, framing long term forecasts in existential risks
- Policy implications may be huge if such forecasts can prove reliable (and we can find proxies for reliability)
- Further analysis, clarification and exploration needed before impact can be claimed

Why we prioritized this paper (in brief)

1. Potential to provide credible *measures* of existential and catastrophic risk, and insight into key debates (e.g. over AI risk)
2. Already seems to be influencing other analyses and decisions (such as Clancy 2023 [2])
3. The XPT data and results seem likely to be used widely in modeling for global prioritization
4. Understanding and harnessing expert judgment is key to other
5. Understanding persuasion and consensus-building may help foster cooperation on global issues

Author engagement, suggestions for evaluators

Ezra Karger supported our efforts, and offered some suggestions for particular areas they would like feedback. We shared these suggestions for feedback, along with a detailed list of our own suggestions, in the [Bespoke Evaluation Notes linked here](#). The author team was particularly concerned with the importance of this work, the usefulness of the data, and the characterization of the relevant debates. Also see the authors' [EA Forum post](#).

The authors have not provided a written response to these evaluations. They are invited to do so, and if they do, we will integrate it here.

How we chose the evaluators

We sought evaluators with expertise and experience in

1. Expert elicitation and aggregation
2. Rare events elicitation methods
3. Existential and catastrophic risks in particular areas, and the quantification of this (Note: neither of the evaluators we recruited had particular expertise in the specific risk areas).

Issues meriting further evaluation

The evaluators (especially Evaluator 2) addressed many of the suggested issues ([here](#)). However, this was a long paper, and an extensive list. We suspect some issues merit further detailed evaluation [3], including...

Data sharing: Is the data shared in a clear and useful way? How could it be made more useful?

Design and implementation, context

- Are they correctly describing the debates in these spaces? Did they ask the right questions? Were the prediction questions well-framed?
- Was the choice of ‘experts’ reasonable? Were these and other groups recruited in ways that would tilt them towards one side or the other, or towards being intransigent?
- Could there be substantial anchoring behavior as a result of their displaying the “Prior Forecasts”?
- Did they do a good job of framing of ‘questions about how they would allocate resources to mitigate potential risks’ (Note some prior literature on ‘eliciting policy choices’ from the public and policymaker participants.)
- What specifically are the most appropriate methods for eliciting these rare event forecasts?

Statistical/quantitative analysis

- Are their aggregation methods appropriate? If not, what approach would be more appropriate.?
- Lack of statistical modeling inference (this was *noted* by evaluators; further evaluators could propose or implement specific approaches)
- Did they adequately consider the potential for attrition bias?

References

1. Karger, E., Rosenberg, J., Jacobs, Z., Hickman, M., Hadshar, R., Gamin, K., Smith, T., Williams, B., McCaslin, T., & Tetlock, P. (2023). Forecasting Existential Risks: Evidence from a Long-Run Forecasting Tournament. Forecasting Research Institute. <https://forecastingresearch.org/publications> (PDF: <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/635693acf15a3e2a14a56a4a/t/64f0a7838ccbf43b6b5ee40c/1693493128111/XPT.pdf>)

Footnotes

1. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. [↪](#)
2. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↪](#)
3. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. [↪](#)
- 4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

⇐

5.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

⇐

6. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ⇐

7. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ⇐

8.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

⇐

9.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

⇐

10. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ⇐

11. This ranking tier rating is de-prioritized in our applied stream (thus Evaluator 2, using the new form, chose not to provide it). ⇐

References

1.

1.

2.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.14289>

1.

3.

E.g., as part of the Unjournal's "Independent Evaluations" initiative.

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